

OXYGEN CAPACITY OF BLOOD DETERMINED BY COPPER SULPHATE METHOD

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Blood samples of 25 apparently normal young healthy men were examined for their oxygen capacity by the specific gravity method. The average is 21.191 c.c. which is a little less than the average of 21.62 obtained by the author.

Phillips, Van Slyke and their co-workers ("Copper sulphate method of determining specific gravity of whole blood and blood plasma") give the following equation for finding out the oxygen capacity, where Ht stands for Haematocrit value, G_b and G_p for the specific gravities of whole blood and plasma respectively,

$$\text{Oxygen capacity} = \frac{(G_b - G_p)}{1.097 - G_p} \cdot Ht$$

The technique consists of dropping drops of whole blood and plasma into graded series of copper sulphate solutions of known specific gravities ranging from 1.008 to 1.076 and differing from one another by 0.004. Each drop in entering the solution becomes enclosed in a sac of copper proteinate and remains as a discrete drop with its specific gravity unchanged for 15 to 20 seconds. The size of the drop need not be constant as the temperature coefficient of expansion of copper sulphate solution is nearly the same as that of the whole blood or plasma. No temperature correction need be applied.

The drops are allowed to fall from a height of 1 cm. from above the surface of the copper sulphate solution. If the drop is heavier, it will continue to fall even after it has lost its momentum due to fall. If it is lighter, it will rise to the surface, and will remain stationary for a few seconds if it has got the same specific gravity as that of the copper sulphate solution. When the drop is dropped care should be taken to avoid air bubbles and the formation of films on the surface of the copper sulphate solution.

The copper sulphate solutions were prepared according to the method given by the authors in their original paper. Additional care was, however, taken to determine the specific gravity of the stock solution by pipetting out 25 c.c. of the solution and determining its specific gravity by weighing it on an analytical balance. From this stock solution, the various other solutions of different specific gravities were prepared by diluting with distilled water.

For our work, we chose 25 apparently normal healthy young male students of the King Edward Medical School, Indore, varying in age between 18 and 28 years. Blood (10 c.c.) was drawn from the vein in specially prepared oxalated bulbs containing 2 mg. of neutral potassium oxalate per c.c. of blood. Within half an hour of taking the blood, the specific gravity of the whole blood was found out. The plasma was separated by centrifuging the blood and within an hour of taking the blood, its specific gravity also was determined. The values of the specific gravity of the whole blood and plasma

were corrected for the oxalate by subtracting 0.004 for each mg. of oxalate present per ml. of blood and the corrected values were used in obtaining the results.

Assuming the haematocrit value to be 46.16, an average arrived in our previous work (Gokhale and Lokre, *Ind. Med. Gaz.*, 1947, 82, No. 9) and then substituting the values of G_b and G_p , the values for the oxygen capacity were calculated. The values obtained are indicated in Table I.

In their original work, the authors of the paper claim the accuracy of this method as compared with the chemical method of Van Slyke to be within a percentage deviation of 0.88.

TABLE I

Sample No.	Oxygen.	Sample No.	Oxygen.
1	21.40 c.c.	13	18.29 c.c.
2	20.15	14	20.05
3	21.40	15	23.34
4	21.40	16	20.79
5	20.66	17	20.66
6	21.38	18	20.79
7	20.40	19	20.79
8	21.40	20	22.24
9	20.79	21	21.24
10	22.34	22	22.24
11	20.79	23	21.40
12	20.06	24	21.38
...		25	21.40

Average 21.191 c.c.

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